

ARSLANQOYRUG – POLYSTYRENE - LEONORUS L. AGROTECHNICS, SEED AND APPLICATION OF THE PLANT

Rasulov Ilham Makhmudovich

Research Institute of Plant Genetic Resources

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7678976>

Abstract. Decree of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated May 16, 2017 no PQ-2970 “on Tsarist measures to increase the production and industrial processing of the root of yalongoch licorice (*shirinmia*) in the Republic of Uzbekistan” dated April 10, 2020 no PQ-4668 “on additional measures for the development of folk medicine in the Republic of Uzbekistan”. Decree of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated May 20, 2022 No. 4670 “on measures for the protection, cultural cultivation, processing and rational use of available resources of wild growing medicinal plants”, PF-139 “on measures to effectively use the raw material base of medicinal plants, to create an additional value chain by supporting processing”, according to the work plan approved in 2023, the enrichment of the insitiut gene pool was planned to be planted in a large experimental area to provide seeds of the National genbankka medicinal arslanquiroous plant.

Keywords: Arslonquid, flavonoid, oxidizing agent, alkaloid, essential oil, n-gumaric acid, vitamin C, iridoid, saponin, quercetin, quincveloside, stachidrin, leonurinin, neurotic, asthenoneurotic, neurasthenia.

OGRITI, employees of the Department of selection, seed production and agrotechnics of medicinal plants together using the experiments of scientists, literature, medicinal arslanquyruk (polystyrene) - Leonurus L.,) plant (yasnotkadoshs - Lamiaceae (labguldashlar — Labiate) is a perennial herbaceous plant that can reach 50-150 (sometimes 200) cm in height. The STEM is several, four-sided, erect-growing, branched. The Leaf is simple, five-lobed, the upper ones are three-lobed, located opposite the bandi on the stem. The flowers are 5-lobed, two-lipped, arranged in a ring shape in the axils of the leaves at the top of the stem, forming a spike-shaped inflorescence.

The fruit is three-sided, consisting of 4 dark brown inflorescences. Blooms in June, August, fruiting is in July, September. Tayèr the product consists of a ground top (stem, leaves and flowers) of a plant trimmed to a length of 30-40 cm. The STEM is four-sided, the inside is hollow, colored red-purple.

Geographical distribution. Arslonkuyruk grows in mountainous districts of Central Asia, conditionally irrigated, suitable for foothills and flat land areas, in densely populated areas in the Caucasus and Western Siberia, in deserted abandoned areas, in cultivated areas with loose soil, on rocky soil slopes from the foothills to the middle part. It was recommended to plant in velvet, Zamin districts of Jizzakh region of the Republic, Pop, Kosonsoy districts of Namangan region, book, Yakkabag districts of Kashkadarya region, Boysun, Sariosiya districts of Surkhandarya region, Bostanlyk, Melonaron District of Tashkent region.

Chemical composition. The chemical composition of the lion's tail plant has not yet been sufficiently studied. The plant has been found to contain flavonoids, up to 2.01—9% excipients, up to 0.035—0.4% alkaloids (when the plant begins to bloom), 0.05% essential oil, n-gumaric acid, vitamin C, iridoids, saponins, bitter, sugar and other substances.

From the sum of the flavonoids of the product, rutin, quercitrin, hyperoside, quercetin 7-glycoside, quercetin and quincveloside, from the sum of alkaloids, leonurinin alkaloid (from the fruit) and up to 0.4% stachidrin are isolated.

To be used. Lion's medicinal preparations of the drug, as a sedative (as with Valerian preparations), are used to treat hypertension, nervous overstrain and some heart diseases (cardiac neurosis, cardiosclerosis). Especially neurotic and asthenoneurotic disorders accompanied by sleep disorders, neurasthenia, neuroses, vegeto-vascular dystonia. Climax accompanied by an increase in Arterial pressure, tachycardia and cardialgic pain is preceded by vegetoneurosis in the period. It is used as part of complex treatment in the initial period of Arterial hypertension.

Medicinal Arslan's technology for the cultivation of the blackberry plant.

It can be planted on all lands of Uzbekistan, except for irrigated (saline soils). To grow a high yield of Arslan, it is important to plant it on fertile light loamy soils, on well-supplied land with water. It will be advisable to plant in areas that have been plowed and emptied.

Arslanit can be planted both in autumn and early spring, since the root system is a perennial herbaceous plant with a Woody rhizome, spreading over the surface, that is, in a 20 cm layer of soil. The land is driven to a depth of 20-25 cm by feeding it with 30 tons of manure and 50 kg of superphosphate fertilizer at the expense of hectares before driving in the fall. The lion's tail is mainly propagated from the seed. In late autumn, dry seeds are sown from 12-18 kg per hectare, and in early spring they are stratified from 7-8 kg to 1.5-2.0 CM.

After sowing seeds on irrigated land, irrigation sows are taken at intervals of 60-70 CM and watered sequentially. If the seed is planted mixed with manure or tree sawdust (from rains that fall in the spring), no sprouts will form, and the seeds will germinate completely. 15-20 days after sowing the seed, the lawn begins to emerge.

In the first year of care for the lion's tail, a manual weeding is carried out, between them are loosened, that is, they are cultivated and yagana is done to sparse out between the plants. The plant spacing is made from 15-20 cm, and 1-2 plants are left in each hive. The petal is fed and watered with nitrogen from 50-60 kg and potassium fertilizer from 20 kg at the expense of hectares, along with cultivation after the release of flowers. The second and third feeding is fed with 30 kg of nitrogen, 20 kg of phosphorus and 30 kg of potassium fertilizer per hectare in the phases of cloning and flowering. During this period, the plant's susceptibility to fertilizer will be highest, and the stems will reach 2-2.5 meters. During the growing season, the medicinal arslanquir is watered 7-8 times, in one hectare of hissbi: a total of 110 kg of nitrogen, 80 kg of phosphorus and 60 kg of potassium fertilizer are given. Depending on this, it is taken as a basis when feeding small experimental areas.

Its raw material is a stem 40 cm long in combination with a leaf, flower stalks. In most plants, when two-thirds of their flowers in the lower parts of the inflorescences Bloom obliquely, the period when the upper part of the inflorescences is shunting is the time when the raw materials are filled. When the seeds are fully mature, the quality of the raw materials is impaired. The raw material allows you to trim the stem in the range of 35-80 CM, that is, with its tool, the lion's tail STEM can be trimmed to an average height of 50 cm. Raw materials can be collected in re-equipped combines. In the first year, its yield is an average of 25 C per hectare, in subsequent years it is possible to harvest from 35 C.

The yield of seeds is 5-6 centners per hectare on average. In one field, the lion's tail can be stored for 3-4 years. Its raw material is dried in soy ground.

Method of application. ICH is applied in the form of a tincture. To prepare the tincture, put 15 g of grass in an enameled container, pour 200 ml (1 glass) of room temperature boiling water over it, cover with a lid and heat in a boiling water bath for 15 minutes, cool at room temperature for 45 minutes, strain through gauze and squeeze out the remaining raw materials. The prepared tincture is brought to a boil with warm water to 200 ml. Drink 1 tablespoon, 3-4 times before ovulation.

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